

Disciplinary Commons Portfolio

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1 Context

The University¹

Robert Gordon University, Aberdeen (RGU) is a post-92 university that was originally founded as Robert Gordon's College in 1881. From 1910 to 1965, it was known as Robert Gordon's Technical College, before a final name change to Robert Gordon's Institute of Technology which it retained until attaining university status as RGU in 1992. The university has a single campus located in the Garthdee area of Aberdeen, situated on the banks of the River Dee. RGU comprises eight academic schools, including the School of Computing, Engineering and Technology.

The Department

The department is the School of Computing, Engineering and Technology. There are approximately 1,000 undergraduate students within the school taking courses in Computing subjects, consisting of home (Scotland), rest

of the UK (rUK), and international (including European). At undergraduate level, approximately 92.5% of entrants are from Scotland, 0.5% are from rUK, and 7% are international.

The School is led by a Dean, supported by a management team consisting of three Associate Deans (one for Academic Development and Student Experience, one for Research, and one for Economic, Social and Cultural Development), an Associate Professor and three Principal Lecturers. Individual courses at undergraduate and postgraduate level are managed by a Course Leader (CL). At undergraduate level, course Leaders are supported by Personal Tutors (PTs), with each PT responsible for a specific year in each course (e.g., Year 2 Computer Science).

The Courses

Overview

At undergraduate level, the School of Computing, Engineering and Technology offers four 4-year² computing courses: BSc (Hons) Computer Science (CS), BSc (Hons) Cyber Security (CY), BSc (Hons) Data Science, and BSc (Hons) Computing and Creative Design (CCD). A 5-year Integrated Masters (MSci) in Computing Science is also offered, and shares the first 3 years with the BSc CS degree.

The module showcased in this portfolio is taught at Year 2 to CS (including MSci) students, but is also available as an elective choice to students taking the other computing courses. However, since it is a core module only for CS and MSci, the remainder of this section will therefore focus on these courses. Additionally, any mention of "CS" also includes MSci, unless an explicit distinction is drawn.

Foundation Year (Year 1)

Foundation Year comprises mandatory modules for all students (2 per semester), mandatory modules for each course (1 per semester), and an elective module (1 per semester). The mandatory module for one course can be chosen as an elective in another.

¹Campus photograph sourced from

<https://www.rgu.ac.uk/rgview/student-experience/4124-our-campus-helps-to-create-a-stunning-student-experience>

²Under the Scottish system, most undergraduate courses last 4 years

Sem1	Introduction to Programming	Problem Solving and Maths	Exploring Computing Devices	<i>Elective module</i>
Sem2	Database Systems	Web UX	Software Design and Development	<i>Elective module</i>

Year 2

Year 2 also comprises mandatory modules for all students (1 per semester), mandatory modules for each course (1 per semester), and an elective module (1 per semester). The module showcased in this portfolio is highlighted in bold.

Sem1	Dynamic Web Development	Advanced Software Design and Development	Real World Projects and Professional Skills	<i>Elective module</i>
Sem2		Data Structures and Algorithms	Research Methods	<i>Elective module</i>

Year 3

Year 3 has a broadly similar structure to year 2, with mandatory modules for all students (1 per semester), mandatory modules for each course (1 per semester), and an elective module (1 per semester).

Sem1	Interdisciplinary Team Project	Machine Learning	Concurrent Programming	<i>Elective module</i>
Sem2	Pirate Studies	AI for Problem Solving	Internet of Things	<i>Elective module</i>

Year 4

Year 4 sees all courses gain a greater focus on their specific route. The BSc (Hons) and MSci deviate at this stage, with students in the former proceeding to their honours year, while the latter have a mandatory industrial, study abroad, or research placement.

For BSc (Hons) Computer Science, Year 4 comprises 4 taught modules in semester 1, with semester 2 being devoted entirely to an Honours Capstone Project.

Sem1	Advanced AI	Computer Vision	<i>Elective module</i>
Sem2	Honours Capstone Project		

For MSci Computing Science, the majority of Year 4 consists of a placement, with only one other module:

Sem1	Industrial Placement, Study Abroad Placement, or Research	
Sem2	Placement	Evidencing Employability

Year 5

Only the MSci Computing Science route has a fifth year of study. Some modules are shared with Year 4 of the BSc (Hons) Computer Science route, however some are also unique to this course.

Sem1	Computing Science Research	Knowledge Modelling and Reasoning	Advanced AI
Sem2	MSci Capstone Project		

The Module

The module is *CM2116 Data Structures and Algorithms*, which occurs in the second year of the 4- and 5-year degree programmes. It is a mandatory module for BSc (Hons) Computer Science and MSci Computing Science, while also being offered as an elective module in other courses.

The Students

All students taking the module study full-time. The majority of students are continuing from Foundation Year, however a small number also join their course at this stage. Such students arrive through one of three main routes:

1. Advanced entry on the basis of higher-than-normal school (or equivalent) qualifications. For example, entry into Foundation Year requires a BBCC at SQA Higher or CCC at A-Level; advanced entry requires BB at SQA Advanced Higher or ABB at A-Level.
2. Articulation from a partner further education college, where the student has attained a Higher National Certificate (HNC).
3. Articulation from International College RGU (ICRGU), which provides alternative entry points for international students. ICRGU offers pathway programmes that replace the ordinary Foundation Year, providing additional help and support to international students as they transition to student life in a foreign country.

The Resources

Learning and teaching materials for the module are fully digital and uploaded to Moodle, the university's chosen learning management system. Recorded lectures are uploaded to Panopto.

All materials are fully accessible. Recorded lectures are automatically captioned when uploaded to Panopto. Lecture slides, lab sheets and other created materials are analysed using Blackboard Ally which generates an accessibility score, and provides suggestions for improving it. Blackboard Ally also generates alternative formats, such as audio (mp3) and electronic Braille.

2 Content

Background

The number of students enrolled in CM2116 in any given academic year will vary, but the expectation is between 60-80 students will be in the class. Teaching is in a single 11-week semester, including a “Connect and Reflect week” in week 6 (i.e., after 5 weeks of teaching). The Connect and Reflect week has no timetabled classes, and is designed to give students an opportunity to consolidate their learning in the semester so far.

CM2116 ran for the first time in January 2023. The module was previously part of a 2-semester module on Advanced Software Design and Development, where the first semester taught advanced object oriented programming in Java, and the second semester taught data structures and algorithms.

Intended Learning Outcomes

On successful completion of this module, students should be able to:

1. Show an extended understanding of different types of commonly occurring data structures and their applications.
2. Undertake the design and development of implementations for commonly occurring data abstractions.
3. Compute mathematical techniques to critically-compare algorithms based on efficiency and scalability.
4. Show an understanding of pseudocode descriptions of methods and algorithms, and implementations thereof.

The aim of the module is to provide students with a knowledge of and ability to implement commonly-occurring data structures and abstractions, and the ability to analyse and critically compare algorithms in terms of complexity and efficiency. Within the context of the module, algorithms are primarily taught in relation to learning outcomes 3 and 4. There is also some relevance to learning outcome 1, through analysing the efficiency of different data structures in terms of (amongst other aspects) algorithms for data storage and retrieval.

Indicative Topics and Content

The indicative topics and corresponding content for CM2116 are shown in Table 1. The numbers in brackets after each topic indicate the week in which the topic is taught (with week 6 being the Connect and Reflect Week with no new content).

The content is designed such that searching, sorting, and recursive algorithms provide concrete examples of different complexities as a way of illustrating the topics on computational complexity and algorithm analysis. This in turn feeds into the topics on data structures, allowing for the complexity of algorithms for data storage and retrieval to be factored into critical comparisons. Java is used to provide implemented examples throughout the module, to demonstrate the concepts.

Module Outline

Learning and Teaching

A flipped classroom approach is adopted in the module, with each week consisting of background study, followed by a 3-hour in-person teaching session involving live demonstrations, class discussions, and lab exercises. Background study always consists of a recorded lecture (of approximately 30 minutes) that introduces that week’s topic(s), but may also include reading from one or more of the course texts. During the 3-hour session, the module coordinator is supported by a demonstrator - a recent graduate or current postgraduate research student - who is familiar with the content and can help run smaller discussion groups, and provide assistance with lab exercises.

In addition to the mandatory 3-hour in-person teaching session, a further “optional lab hour” is scheduled. The ways in which this lab hour is used is student-driven: they can use it to catch-up on any material, and/or obtain general help and support from the module teaching team.

Attendance

Students are expected to complete the background study, and attend all non-optional in-person teaching sessions. An attendance-taking app, *Attendr*, is used to record student attendance. If attendance drops below certain thresholds,

	Topic	Sample content
Algorithms	Introduction to Algorithms (1)	What is an algorithm? Writing and interpreting pseudocode.
	Algorithm Analysis & Computational Complexity (2)	Maths for algorithm analysis. Characteristic operations. Big-O notation.
	Sorting (3)	Bubble Sort. Selection Sort. Insertion Sort.
	Searching (3)	Linear Search. Binary Search.
	Recursive Algorithms (4)	Merge Sort. QuickSort. Comparison of recursive vs. iterative (e.g. Fibonacci, powers).
Data Structures	Introduction to Data Structures (5) Lists (5)	Abstract Data Types. Singly- and doubly-linked lists. Arraylists. Complexity of operations.
	Queues (7)	Implementations (arrays, circular arrays, lists). Priority queues. Dequeues.
	Stacks (7)	Stack operations. Applications of stacks (call stacks, parsing).
	Hash Tables (8)	Hashing algorithms. Collisions and resolution strategies.
	Maps (8)	Hash maps.
	Trees (9)	Complete Binary Trees. Binary Search Trees. AVL Trees. Balancing.
	Heaps (10)	Min-heaps. Max-heaps. Heapify algorithms.
	Graphs (11)	Directed and undirected graphs. Representations (edge arrays, adjacency matrices).

Table 1: Indicitive topics and content for CM2116

students are invited to a meeting with their Personal Tutor.

Work

Students are expected to engage in 150 hours of module-related study per semester, including 30 hours of in-person teaching sessions. The remaining 120 hours (approx. 12 hours per week) include the prescribed background study, as well as self-driven engagement with other materials and resources relevant to the module content. Suggested additional reading and research is provided for each topic, designed to motivate and encourage further exploration and study.

Prerequisites

Much of the content in CM2116 requires knowledge of basic programming concepts and control structures, such as variables, methods/functions, and loops. As such, the module has a formal prerequisite, *CM1112: Introduction to Programming*, that is taught in foundation year (equivalent learning is sufficient for direct entry students). In addition, it is generally expected that students who have reached this stage of their studies have some competency in programming and computational thinking.

Supporting Students

Help and support is provided to students on a hierarchical basis. In the first instance, the module coordinator and/or demonstrator(s) provide subject-specific support during lab sessions. Academic staff also have designated office hours (one virtual, one on-campus) whereby students can drop in and seek further help. Should a student require more general help with their studies, a referral can be made to their Personal Tutor (PT), then - if needs be - their Course Leader.

3 Methods and Teaching Philosophy

Methods

My overall approach is to use blended learning, incorporating a mix of recorded lectures, in-person demonstrations, lab sessions, and further study.

Recorded lectures

Each recorded lecture lasts approximately 30-40 minutes, depending on the specific topic. The aim with each lecture is to provide students with an introduction to that week's topic and motivate their learning. Students are encouraged to note down any questions they might have and send them in advance of the on-campus session. Any questions received then help shape the content for the session.

The lectures are slide-based, but contain examples of certain concepts where appropriate. An iPad and Apple Pencil are used to annotate slides to highlight important aspects or help with understanding.

On-campus session

A single 3-hour on-campus session is scheduled for each week, and is designed under the assumption that all students will have watched the recorded lecture. The exact structure of each session will vary from topic-to-topic, but all contain some form of revision, demonstration(s), class discussion, and lab exercises.

The revision element of the session aims to test understanding of the material in the recorded lecture without identifying individual students. This creates a safe space where students who perhaps didn't watch the lecture (for whatever reason) can be anonymous in making it known that they don't have an understanding. At the start of most sessions, *Menimeter*³ quizzes are used, presenting students with multiple choice questions and the results presented in real time. As well as identifying potential gaps in understanding, this also provides an interactive element from the outset, grabbing students' attention.

Demonstrations consist of physical and practical. Physical demonstrations are designed to show students how an algorithm works, before considering its specification and subsequent implementation. As an example, demonstrating sorting algorithms by selecting some students from the class and having them sort themselves by height. This approach also lends itself well to algorithms for specific contexts. For instance:

- Adding to, searching and traversing a linked list, having the students represent the nodes by holding post-it-notes with the value they are storing, and the name of the next student (node) in the list.
- Same as above but for binary trees, with each student holding post-it notes for the "left" and "right" students (nodes).
- Having students arrange themselves in a queue with a fixed number of places, then demonstrating how a circular array can make this more efficient.

Practical demonstrations are designed to show how algorithms are implemented in (Java) code. These are structured in a "code-along" style, where the students are encouraged to create the implementation at the same time as the lecturer, while also contributing to the code through prompts (e.g., "*what comes next?*" or "*what's missing from this section of code?*"). Live coding in this way also allows the students to observe the lecturer (potentially - although almost always) making mistakes. This not only affords the opportunity to ask the class to correct the mistakes, but it also allows students to see that making mistakes is all part of the coding processes.

Lab exercises for each topic are designed to give students a chance to put their learning into practice. The exercises contain a mixture of questions with written answers (e.g., specifying an algorithm in pseudocode, or stating a computational complexity), and coding exercises. Each lab is structured in a way that sees the difficulty increase as the questions and exercises progress. For example, in a lab on Binary Search Trees, the pseudocode for the left-rotation algorithm might be provided (for implementing), but it will be left to the students to adapt this for right-rotation.

GitHub Classroom⁴ ("*Classroom*") is used for each lab. *Classroom* allows tutors to create assignments (or in this case, lab exercises) based on starter code. When a student accepts an assignment, a GitHub repository with that starter code is automatically created for them. *Classroom* also provides tools to support learning and reflection. Firstly, automated tests

³<https://mentimeter.com>

⁴<https://classroom.github.com>

can be defined that then run when students push code to their GitHub repositories. This allows for immediate feedback on implementations, along with a description of where (if relevant) something has gone wrong. Second, a *feedback pull request* creates a new *Feedback* branch in each student repository which allows a tutor to provide line-by-line feedback on student code (e.g., by adding comments).

Lab solutions are uploaded one full working day before the next on-campus session. This strikes a balance between affording students sufficient time to work on the exercises, while also allowing them to reflect on the solutions before the next class. Solutions come in two forms: answers to the written questions, which are provided on an updated version of the lab sheet PDF, and code, which is provided in a GitHub repository.

Optional lab hour

In addition to the mandatory on-campus session, an optional lab hour is also scheduled each week to provide an environment for supported self-study. The structure of these lab hours is entirely student-driven: it can be used to catch up on labs, carry out additional background study, or ask questions about the module content so far. Attendance at these lab hours is generally quite low, when compared to the mandatory class, but this is one of the reasons for having such a session. It affords an opportunity for less-confident students - who might not want to ask questions in front of the whole class - to seek help and support in an environment that is considerably less crowded.

Assessment

Context

Assessment points for the module are designed under the wider University assessment policy, and Future of Teaching, Learning and Assessment framework. In brief, this requires that 15-credit (i.e., single-semester) modules have only one summative assessment component, unless otherwise fully justifiable. A single component can be split into multiple elements, but these must be of the same form (e.g., all courseworks, or all time-limited exams).

Assessments are graded on an A-F scale as follows:

- A Excellent:** Outstanding performance
- B Commendable/Very Good:** Meritorious performance
- C Good:** Highly competent performance
- D Satisfactory:** Competent performance
- E Borderline Fail**
- F Unsatisfactory:** Fail

Summative assessment: practical exam

For CM2116, it was decided that a single time-limited, partially open-book *practical exam* would be used for assessment. The exam is structured in two parts: part 1 is a set of questions (with a total of 20 marks) designed to test theoretical knowledge of data structures and algorithms; part 2 is a coding exercise to experimentally determine the computational complexity of a given algorithm. The two parts have equal weighting, each contributing 3 sub-grades to the overall grade calculation. The overall grade is determined based on a profile of sub-grades per Table 2.

As noted, the practical exam is partially open-book. This means students have access to the module page on Moodle and can use any resources available there to help answer the questions and complete the coding task. Some resources may be hidden prior to the exam if they are deemed to be too informative (e.g., certain lab solutions).

Formative assessment

Prior to the summative assessment at the end of semester, students are given the opportunity to sit a practice exam. This practice exam is held under identical conditions to the actual exam - same time limit, restricted "exam" user accounts, spaced-out seating etc. While this exam is marked and feedback provided, grades are not assigned due to university policies on formative assessment.

Module grade	Sub-grade profile
A	At least 3 sub-grades at A, at least 4 sub-grades at B or better, and all 6 sub-grades at C or better
B	At least 3 sub-grades at B, at least 4 sub-grades at C or better, and all 6 sub-grades at D or better
C	At least 3 sub-grades at C, and at least 4 sub-grades at D or better
D	At least 3 sub-grades at D, at least 4 sub-grades at E or better
E	At least 3 sub-grades at E or better
F	Sub-grades insufficient to achieve any other grade
NS	Non-submission of work

Table 2: Mapping of grade profiles to module grades

Feedback

As part of the university's Future of Teaching, Learning and Assessment, feedback provision has been standardised across all courses. This requires all assessments to providing a grading grid which in turn is used as a feedback rubric. When grading an assessment, the appropriate feedback from the grading grid should be returned to the student, along with *strengths* and *areas for improvement*.

A spreadsheet is used to streamline this process. The grading grid is transposed into drop-down menus for each student, allowing the most appropriate feedback to be selected for each element. An overall grade is then calculated based on the feedback selected. A further two cells allow for the strengths and areas of improvement to be provided. The full feedback and grade are then uploaded to Moodle where it is presented to the student in HTML format.

Quality assurance

All assessments in the School of Computing, Engineering and Technology go through a process of moderation, with each module assigned a member of academic staff to act as moderator. For modules taught only to foundation or second year, moderation is entirely internal; modules taught at degree and honours year are subject to external moderation. As a second year module, CM2116 requires only internal moderation. This process is shown in Figure 1.

The assessment for CM2116 is a practical exam, and so only an outline is made available to students. This outline describes the format of the assessment and provides the grading grid, to give an indication of what to expect in the exam itself.

Figure 1: Internal Moderation Process